

ATG9A facilitates the biogenesis of influenza A virus liquid condensates near the ER by dissociating recycling vesicles from microtubules

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1. Context

BACKGROUND: Viruses exploit the cellular architecture and pathways to establish biomolecular condensates that allow the spatiotemporal regulation of processes vital to their biology, such as genome replication and assembly or immune evasion [1]. We showed that influenza A virus (IAV) forms specialized cytosolic compartments, named IAV inclusions, that contain viral genome RNA segments (or viral ribonucleoproteins, vRNPs) and vesicles positive for the host protein Rab11a [2-4]. We view IAV inclusions as critical hubs for concentrating and exchanging vRNPs and promoting genome assembly of epidemic and pandemic influenza viruses [5]. Genome assembly is a challenging process as it involves not only the combination of 8 distinct vRNPs but also their transport and packaging into a nascent virion to form infectious particles (Figure 1). We demonstrated that IAV inclusions display the properties of liquid organelles formed by liquid-liquid phase separation [4]. IAV inclusions enlarge as infection progresses, display the ability to dynamically exchange contents and swiftly adjust to physiological changes [4]. Like with other phase separated organelles, IAV inclusions develop in association with host membranes. We have shown that IAV inclusions accumulate near the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) subdomain ER exit sites (ERES) [4], which suggests an interplay between ER and recycling compartment in IAV genome assembly. From an siRNA screen of host factors acting at the ER that impacted IAV infection (not shown here), we identified ATG9A (autophagy related gene 9A) as critical for IAV infection.

GOAL: In this study, we explored the role of ATG9A in the formation of liquid IAV inclusions and provided mechanistic insights into the process of influenza genome assembly.

RELEVANCE: Identifying the key mechanisms driving formation of liquid IAV inclusions may provide means to halt viral production and guide the design of new therapeutics.

REFERENCES: [1] Etibor, T.A. et al. *Viruses* 2021, 13(3): 366. [2] Amorim, M.J. et al. *J. Virol.* 2011; 85(9): 4143-56. [3] Vale-Costa, S. et al. *J. Cell Sci.* 2016; 129: 1884-93. [4] Lanquar, M. et al. *Nat Commun.* 2019; 10(1): 1629. [5] Amorim, M.J. *Front Cell Dev Biol.* 2019; 6: 176.

Figure 1. Our model to explain IAV genome assembly. Over the course of IAV infection, viral inclusions develop in the proximity of the ER subdomain ER Exit Sites. IAV inclusions are biocondensates composed of viral ribonucleoproteins (vRNPs) and vesicles positive for the host protein Rab11 that arise by liquid-liquid phase separation. The liquid nature of IAV inclusions likely facilitates the orchestration of viral genome assembly.

2. Results

2.1. Recycling endosome function is impaired during IAV infection

Figure 2. Rab11a-regulated recycling is impaired during IAV infection. GFP-Rab11a WT and DN cells were infected or mock-infected with PR8 virus for 12h (MOI of 3). **a.** Schematic model of how recycling functions in mock and IAV-infected cells. **b.** Viral production was determined at 12h p.i. by plaque assay and plotted as plaque forming units (PFU) per mL \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Statistical analysis was done by student's t-test ($^{*}p < 0.05$). **c.** Recycling of Transferrin.647 (Tf) at the indicated times was determined by flow cytometry and plotted as the % of recycled Tf for each condition. Statistical analysis was done by Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by a Bonferroni post-comparisons test ($^{**}p < 0.001$).

2.2. Recycling endosomes are re-routed to the ER to form viral inclusions

Figure 3. Rab11a is re-routed to the ER during IAV infection.

a. GFP-Rab11a WT cells (green) were transfected with mCherry-ER plasmid (magenta) and infected or mock-infected with PR8 virus for 12h (MOI of 10). Cells were imaged under time-lapse conditions at 12h p.i. Individual frames with single moving particles are shown in the small panels on the right. The yellow arrowheads highlight fusion/fission events of viral inclusions, as well as their interaction with the ER. Bar = 10 μ m. **b.** GFP-Rab11a WT cells were infected or mock-infected with PR8 virus for 12h (MOI of 3). Cells were processed by high-pressure freezing / freeze substitution and imaged by electron tomography - transmission electron microscopy (TEM). 4 sequential tomograms (120 nm each) were acquired and stitched together to obtain the 3D cumulative model. The 3D model was built using AMIRA software. Bar = 500 nm. Abbreviations: pm, plasma membrane (gray); er, endoplasmic reticulum (blue); v, budding virions (pink); m, mitochondria (purple); smv, single membrane vesicle (green); dmvm, double membrane vesicle (yellow). **c.** The number of single and double membrane vesicles at the indicated times of infection was scored from single sections of transmission electron microscopy.

2.3. ATG9A regulates the formation of liquid IAV inclusions

Figure 4. ATG9A is critical for the formation of IAV inclusions.

A549 cells were treated with siRNA non-targeting (siNT) or targeting ATG9A (siATG9A) for 48h and then infected or mock-infected with PR8 virus for 8-14h, at an MOI of 3-10. **a.** Viral production was determined by plaque assay (PA) and plotted as PFU/mL \pm SEM. Statistical analysis was done by Mann-Whitney test ($^{*}p < 0.05$). **b, j.** The protein levels of ATG9A, NP and actin were quantified by western blotting. **c, d, h.** Colocalization of endogenous Rab11a, PDI, GM130, calnexin and viral NP proteins or of GFP-ATG9A was determined by immunofluorescence using antibody staining. Viral inclusions/ vRNPs are highlighted by white boxes. Cell periphery and nuclei (blue, Hoechst staining) are delineated by yellow and white dashed lines, respectively. Bar = 10 μ m. **e-g.** The roundness and circularity of viral inclusions were determined using the Shape Descriptor tool (ImageJ, NIH) and plotted against each other. Statistical analysis was done by Mann-Whitney test ($^{***}p < 0.001$). **i.** Colocalization between ATG9A and GM130 [Golgi] was determined using FUJ plugins. **n.** GFP-Rab11a WT/DN cell lines were infected and depleted of ATG9A as before and viral production was determined by PA. Statistical analysis was done by one-way ANOVA ($^{*}p < 0.05$, $^{***}p < 0.001$). **k-m.** The levels of LC3-I/II were determined by western blotting and were normalized to actin.

2.4. ATG9A affects vRNP-Rab11a vesicles affinity to microtubules

Figure 5. ATG9A determines the affinity of vRNP-Rab11a vesicles to microtubules. **a-b.** GFP-Rab11a WT cells (magenta) were treated with siNT or siATG9A for 48h. Upon this period, cells were infected with PR8 virus for 10h (MOI of 5) and simultaneously treated with 200 nM Sir-Tubulin dye (green). Cells were treated with DMSO or 10 μ g/ml of nocodazole for 2h before imaging. Cells were imaged under time-lapse conditions at 10h p.i. White boxes show viral inclusions / vRNP-Rab11a vesicles. Individual frames with single moving particles highlighted by yellow arrows are shown in the small panels. Bar = 10 μ m. **c.** Each viral inclusion or vRNP-Rab11a vesicles in a cell (Rab11a as a proxy) was tracked using the TrackMate plugin (Fiji, NIH). Data was plotted as the mean squared displacement (μ m²) per treatment. Red dot = median. 10 cells per condition were analyzed. Statistical analysis was done by a Kruskal-Wallis test ($^{***}p < 0.001$).

2.5. ATG9A does not impact genome packaging into virions

Figure 6. ATG9A depletion affects viral genome assembly but not packaging.

Cells (A549) were treated with siRNA non-targeting (siNT) or targeting ATG9A (siATG9A) for 48h and then infected or mock-infected with PR8 virus (MOI of 3). **a.** The NP intensity in the whole cell at 8h p.i. was measured as the integrated density upon IF staining (FUJ). Statistical analysis was done by Kruskal-Wallis test ($^{***}p < 0.001$). **b.** The levels of the three viral surface proteins at 8h p.i. (HA, hemagglutinin; NA, neuraminidase; M2, Matrix protein 2) were determined by flow cytometry using monoclonal antibodies against each viral protein and analyzed as shown. The median fluorescence intensity (M.F.I.) of each viral protein of the cell surface was plotted for each experimental condition. Statistical analysis was done by one-way ANOVA, followed by a Sidak's multiple comparisons test ($^{**}p < 0.01$, $^{***}p < 0.001$). **c.** The total levels of the indicated viral and host proteins in cell lysates at 8h p.i. were determined by western blotting. Band intensity was quantified using Fiji (ImageJ, NIH) and normalized to actin. **d, e.** The vRNA copy number per mL for each viral RNA segment (1-8) and the vRNA-to-PFU ratio at 8h p.i. was determined by real-time reverse-transcription quantitative PCR using specific primers. Two independent experiments were performed. Statistical analysis was done by a two-way ANOVA test, followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test ($^{*}p < 0.05$, $^{***}p < 0.001$; n.s., not statistically significant). **f.** Scheme illustrating that ATG9A is critical for viral inclusion shape and regulates rate of viral genome assembly but does not affect genome packaging into budding virions.

3. Conclusion & Final Model

In light of our recent findings, we propose that the ER supports the dynamics of liquid IAV inclusions (fusion and fission events and sliding movements). From an siRNA screen of host factors acting at the ER that impacted IAV infection, we identified ATG9A as a regulator of the trafficking of liquid viral inclusions between the ER and microtubules.

Figure 7. Proposed model for ATG9A role in the establishment of liquid IAV inclusions.

We hypothesize that liquid viral inclusions, composed of Rab11a vesicles and vRNPs, might be the sites dedicated to assembly of IAV genome. These structures behave as liquid compartments, having the ability to engage in fission and fusion events to facilitate the exchange of vRNPs and thus promote assembly of complete complexes of 8 vRNPs. In this study, we identified that the host factor ATG9A is mobilized from the Golgi during IAV infection to establish multiple and dynamic contacts with viral inclusions. Likely, ATG9A acts as a linker of viral inclusions between the ER and microtubules.

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